

ELIXIR Training Platform

2024-26

Work Plan

Abstract

The ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP) is building a network of training resources and services, aiming for collaboration, visibility, and standardisation. SPLASH, a digital hub, showcases core services like TeSS, enhancing the training life cycle. Work Packages focus on infrastructure, guidelines, and Train-the-Trainer resources. Collaboration across ELIXIR entities is essential, as are standardised guidelines and a supportive community for knowledge sharing. The project's success will transform training delivery within the community.

This document shows the work plan version as approved by the ELIXIR Board in November 2023.

About this document

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1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

The ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP) has built a massive network that represents a wide range of training resources and services. As we embark on this project, our task is not just to manage this network, but to evolve it, standardise it, and connect all its different components. In doing so, we aim to forge a federated Training establishment that effectively caters to the diverse needs of our community.

Consolidation of the Training Platform Infrastructure (Work Package 2):

The goal is to enhance collaboration and improve the Platform's visibility to end-users. This enhancement is crucial for streamlined information dissemination and robust community engagement. To attain this, the existing Training Metrics Database will be augmented, providing improved support for communities and standards. Concurrently, the SPLASH* digital environment, which integrates services like TeSS, will be established as a "one-stop-shop" for all the ELIXIR Training Platform. The integration of TeSS, a key tool for the ELIXIR training life cycle, will ensure better visibility for the Platform's core services and streamline users' access to diverse services.

Establishment of Comprehensive Training Guidelines (Work Package 3):

This WP aims to develop an inclusive, standardised framework for the complete training life cycle, which is essential to maintain consistency and high-quality standards in training delivery across different Nodes. The guidelines, derived from selected pilot cases, will be demonstrated on the SPLASH website, ensuring the principles are easily accessible and understandable. Furthermore, clear definitions and formalisation of the roles and expectations of Training Coordinators and Training Platform members will be undertaken. This clarity will enhance operational efficiency and facilitate new Training Coordinators' onboarding. These WP activities have clear complementary links to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 'Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and Training' in addition to links to the People and the Node Tier.

Consolidation of Train-the-Trainer (TtT) Programme (Work Package 4):

The goal is to consolidate all TtT resources within the Platform's technical infrastructure, crucial for fostering growth within the TtT community and promoting a supportive knowledge-sharing environment. A dedicated web portal for TtT within the Training SPLASH will be developed, ensuring easy access to TtT materials. The content will undergo FAIRification via a GitHub repository, securing the resources' Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. Finally, an impact assessment strategy will be implemented to measure and improve the programme's effectiveness, leading to better training outcomes.

The achievement of these objectives will require a multi-faceted approach, including collaboration with various ELIXIR entities, cross-talk across ELIXIR ambitions and tiers, consolidation of multiple resources such as complementary links to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 (specifically Task 4.3 'Capacity building in training skills for ELIXIR Node staff', establishment of standard guidelines, and development of a conducive community for knowledge sharing.

(*) SPLASH is a novel digital "rebranding" of the Training Platform. The acronym SPLASH stands for Skills, Professional Development, Learning Assessment, Support and Help along the training life cycle.

Training SPLASH will essentially serve as a website for the Training Platform to provide information on its operations, services, activities and SOPs. The central element of this website will be the training life cycle, which will signpost the different services and working groups that the Training Platform has been working on. TeSS will have a central role in this lifecycle as the Training Platform has invested heavily in TeSS throughout the years. SPLASH will be providing more visibility for TeSS as it will be showcasing it as a core service of the ELIXIR Training Life Cycle.

For additional context, the [Training SPLASH project](#) aims to establish a digital environment representing a "one-stop-shop" for ELIXIR Training Platform (ETrP) services in order to increase its visibility, accessibility and usage and enable more participation within and outside the ELIXIR community. The ETrP has several successful training products, such as TeSS, the Train-the-Trainer programme, the FAIR training project, relevant papers, a training operational handbook containing guidelines etc. We aim to transform access to these resources by creating a single entry point for trainers, trainees, training providers, funders, training developers, and the other ELIXIR Platforms and Communities. SPLASH will present the information sought in

a ready-to-use format that will enable the packaging and visibility of the different training products, using the successful model of the RDMkit, and the ELIXIR Toolkit theme. The created digital resource will be connected with the ELIXIR website and TeSS with the possibility to connect to other services in the future.

In the context of the ELIXIR Programme 2024 - 2028 this work programme aligns with the Technology Priority T3: "Federated service delivery", as well as the People Priority, specifically P1: "Use of ELIXIR services" and P3: "Technical and scientific staff".

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1. Table 1.** Overview of involved institutions. Leads highlighted in **bold**.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
ES	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Lead)	ES-BSC
GR	INAB CERTH (Lead)	GR-INAB
SE	NBIS/Uppsala University (Lead)	SE-NBIS
BE	VIB	BE-VIB
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	CH-SIB
CZ	University of Chemistry and Technology Prague	CZ-UCTP
DE	University of Bielefeld	DE-UBIE
EE	University of Tartu	EE-UTAR
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
EMBL	European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
EMBL	EMBL Heidelberg	EMBL-HD
FI	CSC - IT Center for Science	FI-CSC
FR	CNRS	FR-CNRS
FR	INRAE	FR-INRAE
GR	ATHENA RC	GR-ATRC
GR	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	GR-NKUA
IE	University College Dublin	IE-UCD
IT	ISS (Italian National Institute of Health)	IT-ISS
IT	Sapienza University	IT-SAPU
LU	University of Luxembourg	LU-ULUX
NL	Health-RI	NL-HRI
NO	University of Bergen	NO-UIB
NO	UiT The Arctic University of Norway	NO-UIT
PT	INESC-ID	PT-INES
SI	University of Ljubljana	SI-ULJU

UK	University of Bradford	UK-UBRA
UK	University of Cambridge	UK-UCAM

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - Governance of the Training Platform

WP 1	Lead Partner: ES-BSC, GR-INAB, SE-NBIS	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
ES-BSC - Eva Alloza (Lead)		
GR-INAB - Fotis Psomopoulos (Lead)		
SE-NBIS - Jessica Lindvall (Lead)		
ELIXIR-HUB - Katharina Heil (Coordinator); Manthos Pitoulis		
Objectives		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide regular oversight of the Training Platform activities by chairing the monthly TrCG calls ● Provide feedback on the progress of the Training Platform activities at the annual meeting ● Monitoring the efforts and delivery across partnership ● Support the organisation of the annual meeting of the Training Platform members ● Establish regular channels of communication to the other Platforms in order to ensure alignment ● Provide feedback into the efforts of the Training Platform, as part of the overall outreach activities of the Hub ● Provide recommendations towards the overall Training Platform strategy, consulting with the wider ELIXIR TrP community, and in alignment to the defined long-term goals of ELIXIR (especially in the context of EOSC) ● Review and suggest approaches to further develop and sustain the Training Platform beyond the Work Programme 24-28 ● Pursue and make suggestions on additional avenues of support for the Platform activities, including industry engagement. 		
Description of Work		
<p>The ExCo's role in governing the Training Platform involves overseeing and following up on the tasks in the Work Programme. This includes providing regular oversight through chairing monthly TrCG calls and supporting the organisation of the annual meeting for platform members. Effective communication and alignment with other platforms are emphasised, along with providing feedback and recommendations based on wider community consultation and long-term goals. Additionally, strategic planning is necessary to ensure the platform's sustainability and explore avenues for additional support, including industry engagement and competitive funding calls.</p>		
Activity 1		
<p><i>(leads: ES-BSC (Eva Alloza), GR-INAB (Fotis Psomopoulos), SE-NBIS (Jessica Linvall); members: ELIXIR-Hub (Katharina Heil, Manthos Pitoulis), M1 - M36)</i></p> <p>ExCo's will govern the platform and the work conducted by its members. This includes overseeing and follow-up on the tasks undertaken in the Work Programme.</p> <p>To effectively oversee the Training Platform activities, the responsibility includes chairing the monthly TrCG calls. Additionally, it involves assisting in the coordination of the annual meeting for the Training Platform members. In order to maintain alignment, it is crucial to establish regular channels of communication with the other Platforms. As part of the Hub's outreach activities, providing feedback on the Training Platform's</p>		

initiatives is essential. This feedback should be based on recommendations derived from consulting the wider ELIXIR TrP community and ensuring alignment with ELIXIR's defined long-term goals (Priorities and Ambitions).

Moving forward in the 2024-2026 CoS Project, continuous strategy work needs to be taken as to prepare for the future and consolidate the work ongoing. This is an important aspect with regards to the platform's sustainability and life cycle.

Particular focus will be given in pursuing additional venues of support that will complement the existing and planned activities of the Training Platform. Examples of such venues include traditional competitive funding calls, private-public partnership efforts as well as industry engagement.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Annual report on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	GR-INAB	M13
D1.2	Annual report on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	GR-INAB	M25
D1.3	Writing of the draft project plan for the next Training CoS (early 2026 -> Q4 2026)	ES-BSC	M30
D1.4	End Report <i>(Report on meetings with the ELIXIRHub such as All ExCo's meetings, annual F2F and meetings where ExCo's are summoned)</i>	SE-NBIS	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	Annual Platform meeting	ES-BSC	M12
M1.2	Annual Platform meeting	GR-INAB	M24
M1.3	Annual Platform meeting	SE-NBIS	M36

Work Package 2 - Consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure (services and resources)

WP 2	Lead Partner: BE-VIB, CH-SIB, GR-ATRC
	Start month- End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
BE-VIB, Alex Botzki, Lead (WP and activity 2)	
CH-SIB, Geert van Geest, Lead (WP and activity 2)	
GR-ATRC, Eleni Adamidi, Lead (WP and activity 1), Thanasis Vergoulis, Member (activity 1)	
SE-NBIS, Mihail Anton, Lead (activity 1 & 2)	
SI-ULJU, Brane Leskošek, Lead (activity 1), Member (activity 2); Nadja Žlender, Member (activity 1)	
UK-UCAM, Alexia Cardona, Lead (activity 2)	
FR-CNRS, Olivier Sand, Member (activity 1 & 2)	
IT-SAPU, Allegra Via, Member (activity 1)	
IT-ISS, Loredana Le Pera, Member (activity 1)	
IE-UoL, Maria Doyle, Member (activity 1)	
NO-UIB, David Dolan, Member (activity 1)	
EMBL-HD, Renato Alves, Member (activity 1)	
CZ-UCTP, Vojtech Spiwok, Member (activity 2)	
<p>Objectives (Activity 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review and update the assessment metrics (quality, demographics, impact), as currently hosted by the TMD, taking into consideration the new regulations, standards, etc Expand the functionality of the TMD to allow for customization based on the individual Node/community needs Demonstrate the work in the previous objectives through specific pilot cases (Node?, Bioconductor?), to be performed in a co-production model to the Node Tier. <p>Objectives (Activity 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define and implement the technical requirements, services and governance structures necessary to support the Training Platform content Provide production environment for new platforms (such as the Certification platform, Training SPLASH website etc) Support the automatic population of training events in TeSS by providing instruction documentation on how to use Bioschemas for training events and materials. 	
Description of Work	

This work package focuses on consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure, including both its services and resources. This is specifically important to keep increasing collaboration with the community and make the Platform and its activities visible to all stakeholders. To do so a technical infrastructure to support related activities is essential. This WP comprises the existing **Training Metrics Database** and aims to expand it to better support communities and standards as well as **SPLASH** (the acronym SPLASH is short for **S**kills, **P**rofessional development, **L**earning Assessment, **S**upport and **H**elp along the training life cycle), a digital environment representing a “one-stop-shop” for ELIXIR Training Platform services. Content of SPLASH will be produced in WP3, and the SPLASH website will be constructed in WP2 - the definition of SPLASH can be found in section 1.Objectives.

Activity 1: Expanding the TMD to support communities and standards

(leads: SE-NBIS (Mihail Anton), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), GR-ATRC (Eleni Adamidi); members: FR-CNRS (Olivier Sand), IT-SAPU (Allegra Via), IT-ISS (Loredana Le Pera), IE-UoL (Maria Doyle), NO-UIB (David Dolan), GR-ATRC (Thanasis Vergoulis), SI-ULJU (Nadja Žlender), EMBL-HD (Renato Alves), M1 - M36)

A key component in measuring the impact of the ELIXIR Training Platform is the Training Metrics Database (TMD). The main goal of this Task is to enhance and improve the overall functionality of the service, while also updating and further refining the feedback survey questions to better reflect the changes in the overall regulatory frameworks (GDPR, etc). As an example, the survey questions could be complemented by “impact stories” / narratives tied to the respective training efforts. In order to better facilitate this, a direct connection to existing initiatives (such as the ELIXIR Impact Focus Group and the RIPath) will be assessed. Looking beyond ELIXIR, the additional functionality will also aim to support topic-specific and/or Node-specific survey questions, as well as use by communities not directly tied to ELIXIR (such as the Bioconductor community). The expectation is that TMD will be ultimately supported as a multi-node service delivery plan, with distinct Nodes picking up the various responsibilities, which include software maintenance, service hosting, user support, etc).

Activity 2: Establishing the technical infrastructure and operations of the Training Platform’s Training Life Cycle

(leads: UK-UCAM (Alexia Cardona), BE-VIB (Alex Botzki), SE-NBIS (Mihail Anton), CH-SIB (Geert van Geest); members: FR-CNRS (Olivier Sand), EMBL-HD (Renato Alves), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskosek), CZ-UCTP (Vojtech Spiwok), GR-ATRC (Thanasis Vergoulis), M1 - M36)

The main effort of this WP will be to establish the technical infrastructure components that are currently missing, ultimately providing a coherent space for the content and outcomes of the Training Platform. One key aspect is the requirement for these resources and documentation to be open, easily maintained for sustainable purposes, and tailored for a non-technical audience which will allow better adoption amongst the training coordinators and providers across the Nodes. This activity will work to achieve this by adding the technical functionality in these resources and creating documentation for standard operating procedures that will assist existing and new technical maintainers to be onboarded and provide clear instructions on how to use these technical resources.

Tasks in this WP include:

1. Formalise organisational structure and operations for the ELIXIR Europe Training GitHub Organisation.
2. Formalise organisational structure and standard operating procedures for the ELIXIR Lesson Template maintainers group.
3. Maintain, support and update lesson templates for ELIXIR-branded courses in the [TrP GitHub organisation](#) (e.g. CodeRep lessons). As part of this effort, a BYOCM (bring your own course materials) workshop will be considered as a co-production model to the People/Node Tier as well as the Science Tier (for the relevant experts), in order to promote the use of the lesson template and the certification.
4. Support the integration of Bioschemas markup into ELIXIR-branded training events and materials (minimally those which are hosted in the ELIXIR Training organisation on github, note: others according to capacity) so that it is automatically populated when in use.
5. Production system of the certification platform matching the requirements from the previous WP.
6. Develop, update and maintain the technical framework of the Training SPLASH website.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1	TMD charts that can be embedded into other websites, e.g., ELIXIR Impact page, accompanied by corresponding guidelines	SE-NBIS	M27
D2.2	Version 1: 1-2 Impact stories (e.g., for SPLASH and later embedded into ELIXIR Impact)	SI-ULJU	M18
D2.3	Version 2: 1-2 Impact stories (e.g., for SPLASH and later embedded into ELIXIR Impact)	SI-ULJU	M36
D2.4	Report on "Lessons learnt from trying to run the TMD as a multi-node service"	GR-ATRC	M36
D2.5	Documentation outlining the governance and maintenance structure for the Training GitHub organisation	UK-UCAM	M36
D2.6	Documentation outlining the standard operating procedures for the Training Lesson Template Maintainers	UK-UCAM	M12
D2.7	User friendly instructions on how to use Bioschemas for training events and materials	BE-VIB	M12
D2.8	Production version of a Certification platform that will support the certification process (review, approval, eventual badges, etc.)	SE-NBIS	M36
D2.9	Stable version of the Training SPLASH website	BE-VIB	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	Review and update of the assessment metrics	SE-NBIS	M12
M2.2	TMD support for and suggestions of new assessment metrics, e.g. related to impact	GR-ATRC	M24
M2.3	Version 1: Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	GR-ATRC	M03
M2.4	Version 2: Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	SE-NBIS	M15
M2.5	Version 3: Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	GR-ATRC	M27
M2.6	Version 1: Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	SE-NBIS	M03
M2.7	Version 2: Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	GR-ATRC	M15
M2.8	Version 3: Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	SE-NBIS	M27
M2.9	Training SPLASH website made public	BE-VIB	M12
M2.10	Establish a process of recognition for contribution to lesson templates (link to Data platform)	SE-NBIS	M18

M2.11	Maintain, support and update the ELIXIR Lesson Template	CH-SIB	M18
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Work Package 3 - Consolidating ELIXIR Training standards and best practices for Open science and Open education

WP 3	Lead Partner: GR-NKUA,UK-UCAM, NO-UIT	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
BE-VIB, Alex Botzki, Lead (activity 1) , Member (activity 2); Bruna Piereck, Member (activity 1)		
CH-SIB, Geert van Geest, Lead (activity 1) ; Patricia Palagi, Member (activity 1 & 2)		
GR-NKUA, Vassiliki Iconomidou, Lead (WP and activity 2) , Zoi Litou, Member (activity 2)		
IT-ISS, Loredana Le Pera, Lead (activity 1) , Member (activity 2)		
NO-UIT, Erin Calhoun, Lead (WP and activity 2) , Member (activity 1)		
SE-NBIS, Mihail Anton, Lead (activity 1) , Member (activity 2)		
SI-ULJU, Brane Leskošek, Lead (activity 1) , Member (activity 2)		
UK-UCAM, Alexia Cardona, Lead (WP and activity 1) , Member (activity 2)		
ES-BSC, Eva Alloza, Member (activity 1 & 2)		
IT-SAPU, Allegra Via, Member (activity 1)		
DE-UBIE, Helena Schnitzer, Member (activity 1) ; Daniel Wibberg, Member (activity 1)		
EMBL-HD, Lisanna Paladin, Member (activity 1) ; Renato Alves, Member (activity 2)		
EMBL-EBI, Paulyna Magaña, Member (activity 1) ; Kim Gurwitz, Member (activity 1)		
NL-HRI, Mijke Jetten, Member (activity 1) ; Celia Van Gelder, Member (activity 2)		
FI-CSC, Eija Korpelainen, Member (activity 1)		
<p>Objectives (Activity 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidate the components of the training life cycle • Define the guidelines that need to be followed across the complete training life cycle, that will ultimately be the primary content of the Training SPLASH website • Demonstrate the use of the guidelines through a small number of pilot cases (i.e. topics derived from the Scientific and Technical Priorities and ELSI/EDI), as considered in a co-production model with the People's Tier for the content creation and delivery. In addition, depending on the topic, this objective could have a link to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4. <p>Objectives (Activity 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (ELIXIR perspective) Identify and formalise the roles, responsibilities, and expectations of a Training Coordinator and a member of the Training Platform from the ELIXIR TrP point of view. Connected and complemented to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4, specifically Task 4.1. • (Node perspective) Compile a collection of the additional Node-specific expectations to define the broader context of a TrC's responsibilities. Connected and complemented to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4, specifically Task 4.2 and 4.3. 		

- Define a comprehensive onboarding process for new TrCs, with reference to necessary resources and guidelines covering relevant tools and services to ensure efficient integration into the ELIXIR Training Platform. Connected and complemented to ELIXIR-STEERS WP₄, specifically Task 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Description of work:

The main objective of this work package is to establish comprehensive guidelines for the complete training life cycle, which will be featured on the SPLASH website. These guidelines will be demonstrated through a few pilot cases that address currently missing topics. The aim is to create a framework that encompasses various aspects, such as designing and implementing training resources, maintaining FAIR principles, establishing pathways, and delivering effective training, while also maintaining links and alignment to relevant efforts within ELIXIR (such as the Open Science activity in Node CoS). Additionally, the work package focuses on defining the roles and expectations of a Training Coordinator and Training Platform members from both the ELIXIR TrP and Node perspectives. This includes formalising expectations, creating Node-specific requirements, and developing an onboarding process for new Training Coordinators. The ultimate goal is to establish a clear identity for ELIXIR Training Platform members and facilitate a more formal recognition process.

Activity 1 Unleashing the ELIXIR Training Lifecycle

(leads: UK-UCAM (Alexia Cardona), SE-NBIS (Mihail Anton), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), IT-ISS (Loredana Le Pera), BE-VIB (Alex Botzki), CH-SIB (Geert van Geest); members: BE-VIB (Bruna Piereck, VIB), ES-BSC (Eva Alloza, BSC), IT-SAPU (Allegra Via), FR-CNRS (Olivier Sand), DE-UBIE (Helena Schnitzer, Daniel Wibberg), EMBL-HD (Lisanna Paladin), CH-SIB (Patricia Palagi), EMBL-EBI (Kim Gurwitz, Paulyna Magaña), NO-UIT (Erin Calhoun), NL-HRI (Mijke Jetten), FI-CSC (Eija Korpelainen), M1 - M36)

The main goal of this WP is to build upon the BioHackathon23 Training SPLASH project and provide a framework (as a set of guidance documents/webpages) of the training services that can be used in combination towards a complete ELIXIR training life cycle, i.e., starting planning a training event, to the design and implementation of the individual training resources, to the connection across a pathway while maintaining the FAIR principles, to the skills required to effectively deliver it, to gathering and reporting course assessment. This is meant to reuse/expand/build on the TrP handbook homogenising across the structure provided in the training lifecycle, and serve as content for the technical infrastructure developed in WP2.2.

The ELIXIR Training Lifecycle will become the reference to be followed, accompanied by information and guidance documentation that will be listed and showcase on the Training SPLASH website, including:

- A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps (from material to delivery to assessment). Outreach activities and content creation on how to best utilise the SPLASH content (such as "SPLASH in practice") will be considered for co-development with the respective effort under the People/Node Tiers.
- Best practices towards FAIRification of training resources including FAIRification checklist (in alignment with the FAIR Training focus group, and the TeSS infrastructure)
- Best practices towards the creation of learning paths and their implementation in TeSS (in alignment with the Learning Paths Focus Group, and the TeSS infrastructure).
- Description and definition of the process towards capturing metrics, feedback and impact assessment
- Definition of the Training resource certification, and the respective process (connect this to external networks such as H₃ABioNet, GOBLET, etc)
- Definition of templates and structures for supporting the professional development of Trainers (to be provided as requirements for the efforts under WP2.2))
- Information on how training providers can use Bioschemas for automated integration in TeSS.
- Information on how to use the ELIXIR Lesson Template.
- Information about the TtT programme and the TtT instructors community (WP4.1).

With the current budget constraints it might not be possible to implement all the above in the current programme but we will seek to continue this effort in the upcoming programmes as well as complementary activities in ELIXIR-STEERS (specifically WP₄ 'Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training'.

Activity 2 Defining a Training Platform Standard Operating Procedure

(Leads: NO-UIT (Erin Calhoun), GR-NKUA (Vassiliki Iconomidou); members: BE-VIB (Alex Botzki), SE-NBIS (Mihail Anton), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), ES-BSC (Eva Alloza), UK-UCAM (Alexia Cardona), EMBL-HD (Renato Alves, Lisanna Paladin), IT-SAPU (Loredana Le Pera), NL-HRI (Celia van Gelder), CH-SIB (Patricia Palagi), GR-NKUA (Zoi Litou), M1 - M36)

The Training Platform interacts with diverse communities throughout the ELIXIR ecosystem and aims to consolidate access to services and resources across the training lifecycle. Many standardised processes already exist within the platform, but the majority are based on TrP tradition and culture rather than clearly defined and documented procedures. The growing scale of operations necessitates a shift toward more formalised practices as the Training Platform expands its contributions and the TrP community changes and grows. Establishing a clear framework now will help immerse new members in the ELIXIR training community, provide structure and clarity to new Training Coordinators, and promote quick engagement with TrP activities. Mapping ELIXIR Training Platform activities and formalising member roles also paves the way to introduce a more formal recognition process for member roles and their contributions. The goals in WP3.2 will be complementary linked to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 'Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training'.

The main goals of this effort are to:

- Map critical ELIXIR Training Platform communities, tools, and resources to help identify and define all TrP member activities, outline areas where members could receive recognition for their contributions, and enable both new and existing members to navigate the internal infrastructure effectively. This would increase the support the TrP offers to the entire ELIXIR ecosystem, which has been observed to vary significantly.
- Clearly define the expectations and activities of a Training Coordinator from both an ELIXIR and node-centric perspective, including establishing TrC Terms of Reference and guiding interactions between TrCs and node TrP members, as well as providing support for integral TrP tools and services. This would provide a better engagement from the TrC and also facilitate the inclusion of the Node into TrP activities, which has been observed as being uneven in e.g. work programme participation.
- Implement an onboarding process that ensures that new Training Coordinators will have the information and support necessary to perform their roles. This would ensure transparency of information and make the onboarding process shorter/more efficient, which has been observed as being time-consuming.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1	A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps, connected to the various documents/SOPs/Best practices developed here	UK	M36
D3.2	Version 1: Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	IT	M18
D3.3	Version 2: Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	UK	M30

D3.4	Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	SE	M36
D3.5	Overview of the critical components of the TrP network and relevant resources for TrCs and TrP Node members	NO-UIT	M18
D3.6	ToR document with additional Node-specific expectations	GR-NKUA	M36
D3.7	Onboarding SOP with resources/guidelines for core activities (including TeSS/TMD) for new TrCs	NO-UIT	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1	Consolidate the key components of the ELIXIR Training lifecycle by discussions with Training Excocs and Training Coordinators	UK	Mo6
M3.2	Create editorial guidelines and template for each component of the training life cycle to follow for content consistency in each page	BE	M12
M3.3	Use cases/pilot implemented based on this framework	SI	M36
M3.4	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	BE	M12
M3.5	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	UK	M24
M3.6	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	SE	M36
M3.7	Available in the Training SPLASH, a FAIR training material checklist based on the FAIR training handbook checklist	CH	M18
M3.8	Setup of the organisational structure and standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS	IT	M24
M3.9	Identify and map critical components of the Training Platform that have significant impact on the roles and responsibilities of Training Coordinators and TrP members	GR	Mo6
M3.10	Report on current practices for Training Coordinators and TrP Node members (in relation to activities and onboarding), highlight areas for recognition, and redefine the existing onboarding process	NO	M12
M3.11	TrC Terms of Reference draft; share for feedback and revisions	GR	M24
M3.12	Onboarding SOP draft; share for feedback and revisions	NO	M24

Work Package 4 - Train-the-Trainer programme consolidation

WP 4	Lead Partner: CH-SIB, EMBL-HD, IT-SAPU	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
CH-SIB - Patricia Palagi (Lead)		
EMBL-HD - Lisanna Paladin (Lead)		
IT-SAPU - Allegra Via (Lead)		
UK-UBRA - Krzysz Poterlowicz (Lead) ; Katarzyna Kamieniecka (Member); Khaled Jumah (Member)		
DE-UBIE, Daniel Wibberg, Helena Schnitzer (Member)		
EE-UTAR, Priit Adler (Member)		
EMBL-EBI, Piv Gopalasingam, Patricia Carvajal (Member)		
FR-INRAE, Helene Chiapello (Member)		
IT-ISS, Loredana Le Pera (Member)		
LU-ULUX, Roland Krause (Member)		
NO-UIT, Erin Calhoun (Member)		
SE-NBIS, Jessica Lindvall (Member)		
SI-ULJU, Brane Leskosek (Member)		
UK-UCAM, Alexia Cardona (Member)		
PT-INES, Daniel Faria, Gil Poyares-Oliveira (Member)		
CZ-UCTP, Vojtech Spiwok (Member)		
Objectives		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidate all TtT resources under the unified TrP technical infrastructure (Training SPLASH) • Expand the TtT effort to include impact assessment and onboarding (complementary links to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4, Task 4.1 and 4.3) 		
Description of Work		
<p>The objectives of this task are to consolidate all Train the Trainer (TtT) resources within the Training Platform's technical infrastructure, expand the TtT efforts to include impact assessment and onboarding, and foster the growth of the TtT community (considered for co-development with TtT content creation and training delivery under the People/Node Tiers in addition to the links to ELIXIR-STEERS WP4, Task 4.1 and 4.3). The activities for the TrP WP4 will involve populating dedicated web pages/portals for TtT within the Training SPLASH, ensuring easy access and maintenance of TtT materials. It will also include FAIRification of content through a GitHub repository, developing additional resources for specific needs, implementing</p>		

an impact assessment strategy, and creating a supportive environment for TtT instructors to share experiences and knowledge.

Activity 1 Consolidating the TtT programme, materials and content

(Leads: CH-SIB (Patricia Palagi), IT-SAPU (Allegra Via), UK-UBRA (Krzys Poterlowicz) and EMBL-HD (Lisanna Paladin); members: DE-UBIE (Daniel Wibberg, Helena Schnitzer), EE-UTAR (Priit Adler), EMBL-EBI (Piv Gopalasingam, Patricia Carvajal), FR-INRAE (Hélène Chiapello), IT-ISS (Loredana Le Pera), LU-ULUX (Roland Krause), NO-UIT (Erin Calhoun), SE-NBIS (Jessica Lindvall), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), UK-UCAM (Alexia Cardona, Katarzyna Kamieniecka, Khaled Jumah), PT-INES (Daniel Faria, Gil Poiares-Oliveira), CZ-UCTP (Vojtech Spiwok), M1-M36)

This Task will be focused on consolidating the TtT resources, in alignment with the 5 steps of the TrP Life Cycle, to facilitate reuse by ELIXIR Nodes and beyond, and onboarding of TtT instructors. The task has clear links with ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 activities.

Actions that will run under this task include:

- Populate the dedicated TtT webpages/portal in the Training SPLASH - This will allow the consolidation and sharing of the TtT material under a single entry point where all the TtT materials can be found, while ensuring easy maintenance (i.e. packaging the resources for re-use).
- Populate the dedicated TtT webpages/portal in the Training SPLASH with the TtT trainers, events, information, etc., thus ensuring the TtT courses and events are findable.
- Development of further materials for specific needs, including new TtT professional guides, additional TtT standalone sessions (e.g. Presentation skills, Lesson development, Training material design, Teaching online or hybrid...). Creation and development of new training modules and material in addition to delivering these will be considered for co-development with the respective effort under the People/Node Tier.
- Create a professional guide with a step-by-step procedure to FAIRify training materials (based on the [FAIR training handbook](#)), and apply it to the FAIRification of TtT materials.
- Set up a strategy and identify indicators to assess the impact of the TtT programme, in collaboration with WP2.1, and evaluate their efficacy with the ELIXIR Impact officer.

Activity 2

Expected leads: UK (Krzys Poterlowicz) & DE (Lisanna Paladin); expected members: CH (Patricia Palagi), IT (Loredana Le Pera, Allegra Via), DE (Daniel Wibberg, Helena Schnitzer, Renato Alves), EE (Priit Adler), EMBL-EBI (Piv Gopalasingam, Patricia Carvajal), FR (Hélène Chiapello), LU (Roland Krause), NO (Erin Calhoun), UiT The Arctic University of Norway, SE (Jessica Lindvall), SI (Brane Leskošek), UK (Alexia Cardona, Katarzyna Kamieniecka, Khaled Jumah), NL (Mijke Jetten, Celia van Gelder), PT (Daniel Faria, Gil Poiares-Oliveira)
Nurturing of the TtT instructors' community → this activity will be funded and covered as part of the ELIXIR 2024-2028 Programme People Tier.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D4.1	A professional guide with a step-by-step procedure to FAIRify training materials ready	CH-SIB	M12
D4.2	FAIRified TtT materials	IT-SAPU	M24
D4.3	Sections in the Training SPLASH with the data from the TtT Instructors and TtT course feedback and assessments	EMBL-HD	M12
D4.4	The TtT webpages/portal in the Training SPLASH	UK-UBRA	M24
D4.5	At least two Guides developed	IT-SAPU	M36
D4.6	A final strategy and set of measurable indicators to assess the impact of the TtT programme	CH-SIB	M36

Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M4.1	A detailed outline of the guides that will be developed during this period	CH-SIB	M12
M4.2	A first version of the strategy and indicators to assess the impact	IT-SAPU	M24

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.3	Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	GR-ATRC	M03
M2.6	Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	SE-NBIS	M03
M3.1	Consolidate the key components of the ELIXIR Training lifecycle by discussions with Training ExcOs and Training Coordinators	UK	M06
M3.9	Identify and map critical components of the Training Platform that have significant impact on the roles and responsibilities of Training Coordinators and TrP members	GR	M06
M1.1	Annual Platform meeting	ES-BSC	M12
D2.6	Documentation outlining the standard operating procedures for the Training Lesson Template Maintainers	UK-UCAM	M12
D2.7	User friendly instructions on how to use Bioschemas for training events and materials	BE-VIB	M12
M2.1	Review and update of the assessment metrics	SE-NBIS	M12
M2.9	Training SPLASH website made public	BE-VIB	M12
M3.2	Create editorial guidelines and template for each component of the training life cycle to follow for content consistency in each page	BE	M12
M3.4	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	BE	M12
M3.10	Report on current practices for Training Coordinators and TrP Node members (in relation to activities and onboarding), highlight areas for recognition, and redefine the existing onboarding process	NO	M12
D4.1	A professional guide with a step-by-step procedure to FAIRify training materials ready	CH-SIB	M12
D4.3	Sections in the Training SPLASH with the data from the TtT Instructors and TtT course feedback and assessments	EMBL-HD	M12
M4.1	A detailed outline of the guides that will be developed during this period	CH-SIB	M12
D1.1	Annual report on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	GR-INAB	M13
M2.4	Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	SE-NBIS	M15
M2.7	Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	GR-ATRC	M15

D2.2	1-2 Impact stories (e.g., for SPLASH and later embedded into ELIXIR Impact)	SI-ULJU	M18
M2.10	Establish a process of recognition for contribution to lesson templates (link to Data platform)	SE-NBIS	M18
M2.11	Maintain, support and update the ELIXIR Lesson Template	CH	M18
D3.5	Overview of the critical components of the TrP network and relevant resources for TrCs and TrP Node members	NO-UIT	M18
M3.7	Available in the Training SPLASH, a FAIR training material checklist based on the FAIR training handbook checklist	CH	M18
M1.2	Annual Platform meeting	GR-INAB	M24
M2.2	TMD support for and suggestions of new assessment metrics, e.g. related to impact	GR-ATRC	M24
D3.2	Version 1: Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	IT	M18
M3.5	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	UK	M24
M3.8	Setup of the organisational structure and standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS	IT	M24
M3.11	TrC Terms of Reference draft; share for feedback and revisions	GR	M24
M3.12	Onboarding SOP draft; share for feedback and revisions	NO	M24
D4.2	FAIRified TtT materials	IT-SAPU	M24
D4.4	The TtT webpages/portal in the Training SPLASH	UK-UBRA	M24
M4.2	A first version of the strategy and indicators to assess the impact	IT-SAPU	M24
D1.2	Annual report on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	GR-INAB	M25
D2.1	TMD charts that can be embedded into other websites, e.g., ELIXIR Impact page, accompanied by corresponding guidelines	SE-NBIS	M27
M2.5	Presentation of new charts of the TMD data for TrP F2F	GR-ATRC	M27
M2.8	Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year	SE-NBIS	M27
D1.3	Writing of the draft project plan for the next Training CoS (early 2026 -> Q4 2026)	ES-BSC	M30

D1.4	End Report (Report on meetings with the ELIXIRHub such as All ExCo's meetings, annual F2F and meetings where ExCo's are summoned)	SE-NBIS	M36
M1.3	Annual Platform meeting	SE-NBIS	M36
D2.3	1-2 Impact stories (e.g., for SPLASH and later embedded into ELIXIR Impact)	SI-ULJU	M36
D2.4	Report on "Lessons learnt from trying to run the TMD as a multi-node service"	GR-ATRC	M36
D2.5	Documentation outlining the governance and maintenance structure for the Training GitHub organisation	UK-UCAM	M36
D2.8	Production version of a Certification platform that will support the certification process (review, approval, eventual badges, etc.)	SE-NBIS	M36
D2.9	Stable version of the Training SPLASH website	BE-VIB	M36
D3.1	A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps, connected to the various documents/SOPs/Best practices developed here	UK	M36
D3.3	Version 2: Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	UK	M30
D3.4	Guidelines on standard operating procedures for Learning Paths Editorial Board for creating and maintaining Learning Paths in TeSS. Guidelines on how to integrate the LP process within the whole Training Lifecycle framework. Production of webpage content on LP to be shown on Training SPLASH	SE	M36
D3.6	ToR document with additional Node-specific expectations	GR-NKUA	M36
D3.7	Onboarding SOP with resources/guidelines for core activities (including TeSS/TMD) for new TrCs	NO-UIT	M36
M3.3	Use cases/pilot implemented based on this framework	SI	M36
M3.6	Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page	SE	M36
D4.5	At least two Guides developed	IT-ISS	M36

Appendix B: Partner information

Table Partner information

Institution	Contact Name
ES-BSC	Eva Alloza
GR-INAB	Fotis Psomopoulos
SE-NBIS	Jessica Lindvall
SE-NBIS	Mihail Anton
BE-VIB	Alex Botzki, Bruna Piereck
CH-SIB	Geert van Geest
CH-SIB	Patricia Palagi
CZ-UCTP	Vojtech Spiwok
DE-UBIE	Daniel Wibberg
DE-UBIE	Helena Schnitzer
EE-UTAR	Priit Adler
ELIXIR-HUB	Katharina Heil
EMBL-EBI	Paulyna Magaña, Kim Gurwitz, Piv Gopalasingam, Patricia Carvajal
EMBL-HD	Lisanna Paladin, Renato Alves
FI-CSC	Eija Korpelainen
FR-CNRS	Olivier Sand
FR-INRAE	Hélène Chiapello
GR-ATRC	Eleni Adamidi, Thanasis Vergoulis
GR-NKUA	Vassiliki Iconomidou, Zoi Litou
IE-UoL	Maria Doyle
IT-ISS	Loredana Le Pera
IT-SAPU	Allegra Via
LU-ULUX	Roland Krause
NL-HRI	Celia Van Gelder

NL-HRI	Mijke Jetten
NO-UIB	David Dolan
NO-UIT	Erin Calhoun
PT-INES	Daniel Faria, Gil Poiares-Oliveira
SI-ULJU	Brane Leskošek, Nadja Žlender
UK-UBRA	Krzysz Poterłowicz, Katarzyna Kamieniecka, Khaled Jumah
UK-UCAM	Alexia Cardona